

D8.6

The FAIRness of IAGOS

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Deliverable abstract

This report presents the implementation of the FAIR principles by IAGOS.

DELIVERY SLIP

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D8.6 – The FAIRness of IAGOS

1 Introduction

The ENVRI-FAIR project’s objective is to implement “FAIRness” for data produced in the European Research Infrastructures (RIs) organized in the Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) community, in order to make them ready for connecting to the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#). In this context, “FAIR” is an acronym comprising the aspects of “Findable”, “Accessible”, “Interoperable”, and “Reusable” as specified by the [FORCE11 community](#).

ENVRI-FAIR WP8 organises and conducts this implementation work for the community of ENVRI RIs in the atmospheric subdomain, comprised of the RIs [ACTRIS](#), [EISCAT](#), [IAGOS](#), [ICOS \(atmosphere\)](#), and [SIOS \(atmosphere\)](#).

[D8.3 Atmospheric subdomain implementation plan](#) describing the implementation plan of FAIRness for the atmospheric sub-domain was ready March 2020. Later there is a revised version produced, taking the implementation of the ENVRI-Hub into account. [This 2nd version was finalized September 2021](#), and is the most recent implementation plan for WP8.

Towards the end of the project, a set of deliverables are due M50 describing the implementation of FAIRness, for each RI.

- D8.4: The FAIRness of ACTRIS
- D8.5: The FAIRness of EISCAT_3D
- D8.6: The FAIRness of IAGOS
- D8.7: The FAIRness of ICOS-atm
- D8.8: The FAIRness of SIOS

This deliverable provides the “The FAIRness of IAGOS” and refers to the status of the implementation in relation to the updated, 2nd version of the implementation plan from September 2021.

Furthermore, a FAIRness assessment is performed in the first part of 2023 to monitor the complete progress over the project period using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs). This is ready in April and will be reported in the Deliverable “D8.13 Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment report” due May 2023.

2 Background and the starting point for IAGOS

2.1 Gap analysis

The RIs of the ENVRI atmospheric subdomain conducted a comprehensive analysis of the FAIRness of their data centre, data curation and management late 2018 during the proposal writing.

Since the beginning of ENVRI-FAIR, IAGOS conducted three FAIRness assessments using the FIPs in 2019, 2020 and 2021. The last one (for 2022) is currently in progress and will be finished by April. Based on the gap analysis and the first FIP, a detailed implementation plan was developed for IAGOS. The assessments allowed to monitor the progress of IAGOS FAIRness during the project and check the consistency with the implementation plan.

The main gaps that have been identified for IAGOS were:

- No use of PIDs in the IAGOS data processing workflow
- No implementation of standard interfaces for metadata and data access
- No common authentication scheme with the other RIs implemented
- No documentation of the provenance

A new version of the IAGOS data portal was already planned at the beginning of ENVRI-FAIR. All the developments were aligned with the implementation plan.

2.2 The FAIR implementation plan for IAGOS

Here is the list of the main tasks of the IAGOS implementation plan with the associated milestones during ENVRI-FAIR:

- Consolidation of consistent use of PIDs throughout data production workflow:
 - Definition of the new IAGOS data production workflow with PID management: assign PIDs to all data files in order to trace the workflow provenance of all the data products
 - Registration to ePIC: to be able to assign ePIC PIDs to data files of fine level (e.g. data file for a IAGOS flight) where DOIs are provided to citable data products (i.e. collection of all the data files of a certain type and processing level)
 - Implementation of ORCID for humans and ROR for organisations: to be included in the provenance information
 - Management of DOI fragments and implementation of a querystore: to be able to cite subset of collection and redo a user query
 - Consistent use of PIDs and new data production workflow
- Common standard interfaces for metadata and data access
 - *REST API for metadata access*
 - *REST API for data access*
 - *THREDDS server deployed with access to all IAGOS products*
- Indexing of data resources in WIS, GEOSS
 - *Implementation of WIGOS metadata profile*
 - *Link with WIS established*
- Common use of authentication schemes
 - *AERIS authentication implemented in new IAGOS Data Portal and then ORCID and eduGAIN authentication*
- Endpoint for providing service metadata to ENVRI-hub
 - *Setting up the PythonAPI endpoint serving metadata and linking to data, serving both WP8 demonstrator and ENVRI-hub*
 - *Create the records describing IAGOS data provision services in ENVRI catalogue of services*
- Recommendations on RIs graphical user interfaces (GUI)
 - *Release of the new IAGOS Data Portal*
- Documenting provenance
 - *Management of DOI fragments and implementation of a querystore*
 - *Consistent use of PIDs and new data production workflow implemented*
 - *Release of the new IAGOS Data Portal*
- Additional tasks regarding:
 - *Domain vocabulary / ontology for observed parameters, discovery and use metadata*
 - *Recommendations for licenses on metadata and data*
 - *Semantic search for atmospheric ENVRI RI user interfaces*
 - *Improve Graphical User Interfaces*

3 Progress on FAIRness for IAGOS

This section includes the progress reports of implementation of FAIRness within IAGOS in relation to the implementation plan and identification of potential open issues and need for changes in the implementation plans for each RI.

The section includes a table with symbols referring to the sections in in [D8.3 Atmospheric subdomain implementation plan](#)

During the first year of the project, IAGOS started the implementation of the priority tasks: the definition of the workflow with PIDs, the development of the REST API for data and metadata access and the implementation of the common authentication scheme.

During the second year of the project, all tasks have been started. Most of them were almost completed but were waiting for the release of the new IAGOS Data Portal. A new important task, documentation of the provenance, has been started and aligned with the tasks relevant to the new IAGOS data workflow. The implementation of the ENVRI Catalogue of services triggered new tasks to describe IAGOS services in the Catalogue. Finally, development of the FAIR ENVRI Atmosphere Demonstrator implemented to demonstrate the interoperability between data of Atmosphere RIs required a new task: *implementing a Python API endpoint serving metadata and data and linking to data*.

During the third year of the project, most of the tasks have been completed thanks to the release of the new IAGOS Data Portal. It includes the deployment of the new data processing workflow including the use of PID and documentation of the provenance of the IAGOS datasets; the common authentication scheme using a solution provided by AERIS (the French Data and Services Cluster for Atmosphere) with authentication through ORCID or eduGAIN; the deployment of the REST API for metadata and data access; and the choice of the standard data license Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) in alignment with the other Atmosphere RIs. For the new Data Portal, expertise from the GUI working groups has been used. Standard vocabularies are used for variables, instruments and platforms types.

The next table represents the current progress status of the main tasks identified in the Implementation plan. Most of the tasks are currently completed. The remaining tasks are presented in the next section.

The symbols used are:

	Completed
	In progress
	Not started, according to plan (0)
	New tasks not in the implementation plan

Table 1: Summary of implementation of FAIRness by IAGOS

IAGOS				
Progress on implementaion of FAIRness		March 2023		
Completed				
In progress				
Not started, according to plan				
New task, not in the implementation plan				
Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month	2020	2021	2022
Implementation plan				
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
IAGOS: ePIC registration, internal ORCID PIDs	2nd QTR 21			
IAGOS: definition of workflow, incl. PID	3rd QTR 20			
IAGOS: workflow with PIDs, implemented	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: implement ORCID and ROR	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: management of DOI fragments	4th QTR 21			
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
IAGOS: REST API for metadata access implemntd.	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: THREDDS server for data access implmntd.	2nd QTR 23			
IAGOS: REST API for data access implemented	4th QTR 21			
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
IAGOS: WIGOS metadata implemented	2nd QTR 23			
IAGOS: link to WIS established	4th QTR 22			
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
IAGOS: ORCID / eduGAIN authentication avail.	1st QTR 22			
1.5 Service endpoint to ENVRI-hub				
IAGOS: set up PythonAPI endpoint	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: provide service record	1st QTR 23			
1.6 GUI recommendations				
IAGOS: release of new portal	1st QTR 22			
1.7 Document provenance				
IAGOS: management of DOI fragments	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: consistent use of PIDs	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: new IAGOS Data Portal	1st QTR 22			
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	3rd QTR 22			
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 22			
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 22			
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21			
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	1st QTR 22			

4 Remaining tasks

Tasks still in progress

One task is still in progress and will be completed in the next month: *Provide IAGOS services record to the ENVRI catalogue of services.*

IAGOS is currently creating records describing IAGOS data access services in the ENVRI catalogue of services. This task has been delayed due to some technical issues with the onboarding system provided by the Catalogue of service that are now fixed.

Tasks which need revision of plans

One task has been delayed and may not be completed by the end of the project: *Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS.*

The implementation of the WIGOS profile is still in progress. Some points need to be clarified with WMO (for instance mobile platforms aren't managed by the WMO catalogue). Once the WIGOS profile is implemented, metadata will be provided to the OSCAR portal in the frame of GAW.

Also, actual use of WIS and GEOSS in our field of work this should get lower priority. The implementation is then delayed without any expected impact.

Another task is reevaluated: *Implementation of a THREDDS server for data access.*

The implementation of a THREDDS server has been postponed due to multiple reasons:

- IAGOS data are mostly 1D time series and then not concerned by some services provided by THREDDS relevant for 2D data (WMS, WCS). Some IAGOS Derived data products such as climatologies are 2D data but their number is very limited. However OPeNDAP access is relevant for the time series provided in the NetCDF format.
- Other solutions are currently being considered such as ERDDAP. IAGOS is involved in French projects where mutualized solutions could be provided. Therefore, the task is postponed until more feedback is available

5 Main achievements and improvement of FAIRness for IAGOS

5.1 What can we do now which we could not before advancing of the FAIRness?

The implementation and increase of the FAIRness for IAGOS can be demonstrated by many results:

- The interoperability between IAGOS data and other Atmosphere RIs data has been demonstrated with the FAIR demonstrator developed by IAGOS. It allows to cross search, visualize, compare and download data from all the RIs.
- The IAGOS Data Centre now provides traceable data products to the users. All data products and finer datasets are provided with rich standardized provenance metadata included in data files and PID landing pages. All datasets are assigned PIDs. This improved the quality of the IAGOS data and metadata.
- IAGOS data and metadata are available through standard services (e.g. RESTful API)
- Vocabularies used by IAGOS are mapped to vocabularies used by the other RIs. (for the name of the variables and the type of instruments and platforms)
- A standardized and secure system for authentication and authorization has been implemented for accessing IAGOS data and services.
- IAGOS data are licensed under the same data license than the other RIs. It will facilitate the implementation of cross RI services in the future.

5.2 What would we like to do / achieve within the next 5 years?

Some tasks still need to be completed by IAGOS within the next years:

- Connect the IAGOS Single Sign On system to the ENVRI and EOSC AAI
- Integrate all IAGOS resources (services and datasets) in the EOSC marketplace
- Provide more data and metadata access interfaces (OPeNDAP, OGC services, etc.)
- Improve the provenance metadata by assigning PIDs to instruments and platforms
- Improve the vocabularies and publish them in a standard way (e.g. data quality flags)
- Implement Jupyter Notebooks to demonstrate the use of IAGOS services
- Implement sustainable cross RI services
- Improve the discovery of data on the IAGOS Data Portal (semantic search, etc.)